

Inclusive Teaching at the Graduate Level

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Introduction

Graduate students are a fundamental part of the higher education system, performing both research and teaching duties. However, despite relying heavily on graduate students for undergraduate education, there is often little emphasis placed on preparing graduate students for their roles as teaching assistants (Beers et al., 2020) or communicating the available resources for improving their teaching skills. This undervaluing of graduate student teaching development has lasting impacts on the future of higher education, as graduate students who pursue careers in academia will invariably be required to teach. Without a strong understanding of effective and inclusive teaching, professors may inadvertently produce courses which are inaccessible, inequitable, and unnecessarily difficult for the diverse student body enrolled in higher education.

To address the chronic gap in teaching development of graduate students and to secure a more equitable future of higher education, this document has been created in conjunction with the Department of Geosciences' Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion (DEI) Committee as an introductory resource for graduate student instructors. The intention is to give all graduate student instructors a base understanding of best practices in teaching in order to foster a more diverse, equitable, and inclusive geoscience community at large.

Here, you will find information about how teaching and DEI intersect, how to cultivate an inclusive classroom climate, and how to maximize student learning. For those interested in more information, there are additional resources listed at the end which go into further detail on the topics introduced here.

Teaching as a Matter of Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion

Diversity, equity, and inclusion (DEI) is a conceptual framework for how members of a group are perceived, treated, and valued that aims to include all people in a group or organization (Emery et al., 2020).

Diversity is the vast array of differences that exist between individuals and whole social groups. *Structural diversity* is a numerical metric of measuring diversity at an institution that assesses diversity as a sort of “numbers game” (Hurtado et al., 1999). This is typically what you think of when an institution touts itself as ‘diverse.’ *Informal interactional diversity* is a semi-quantitative metric of measuring diversity which accounts for not only the frequency but also the quality of interactions between diverse groups (Gurin et al., 2002). This is

considered a better estimate of diversity within an institution than structural diversity alone, although it is more difficult to determine.

Equity is the fair and just practices that ensure “equality of opportunity” for all students (Clancy & Goastellec, 2007). Equity accounts for the highly variable backgrounds and identities of group members and accommodates each individual specifically to ensure success. Additionally, equity involves the identification and dismantling of biases which prevent group members from fully participating. Equality and equity differ in that equality assumes genuinely uniform treatment of all group members will result in success, which does not account for systematic marginalization of specific groups (Espinoza, 2007). Equity serves to give each group member the specific support they need to overcome their unique barriers to success.

Inclusion is the intentional practice of including and accommodating all differences in a group setting, particularly by identifying and mitigating biases both personally and culturally within the group (Dewsbury & Brame, 2019).

Institutions of higher education are historically built on systems which, either purposefully or unintentionally, alienate marginalized groups. For this reason, intentional DEI work today is crucial for creating environments where all students are respected, encouraged, and successful. Focused DEI efforts will yield more welcoming educational environments and a more diverse geoscience community at large by accommodating a larger community of people who are typically underserved in STEM.

Markers of undergraduate success in STEM programs, such as persistence within a program, degree attainment, and continuation to graduate study, depend heavily on students developing and maintaining a sense of belonging in the program (Walton & Cohen, 2011; Booker, 2016; Rainey et al., 2018; Fisher et al., 2019). This is true of all students, but is especially important for marginalized or minoritized students who are not traditionally reflected in STEM spaces (Booker, 2016; Walton & Cohen, 2011). Therefore, encouraging belonging is a critical DEI measure to work towards.

Belonging is largely influenced by interactions between students and instructors (Wilson & Gore, 2013). This refers to every interaction between students and instructors, not strictly those during class time or pertaining to course content. It has been found that students develop the strongest sense of belonging when instructors are accessible, approachable, and deliver “authentic instruction” (Booker, 2016).

Accessibility and approachability are reflected in instructor empathy, kindness, and willingness to assist and interact with students outside of the classroom. Within the

classroom, an instructor's clear establishment of an inclusive culture and prompt reaction to microaggressions also increase marginalized students' feeling of belonging.

"Authentic instruction" addresses the act of teaching itself, rather than an instructor's attitude or beliefs. Belonging is increased when instructors include real world examples applicable to their student's backgrounds and goals, use variable methods of instruction and assessment, and encourage discussion and collaboration between students.

Student belonging is enhanced both by an instructor's intentional choice to be inclusive and accessible, but also by the instructor's pedagogical style. Therefore, it is important that instructors actively engage in professional development which emphasizes inclusive and effective teaching.

Graduate students who teach are in an additionally unique position over faculty instructors. For one, graduate student TAs often have much more direct interaction with the students than the instructor, particularly in high enrollment courses. Even in smaller classes, undergraduates often feel they can more easily approach a TA than the faculty instructor (Franz et al., 2022). Furthermore, in lab sections, TAs guide students through tangible achievements in a relatively small group setting, which directly encourages student confidence and identity as a scientist (Kortz et al., 2020).

Graduate students therefore play a critical role in enhancing student belonging. In turn, enhanced student belonging will yield a more diverse field of geosciences at large. This means graduate student level instruction should be a priority for all DEI initiatives, and it is important to communicate this role to all graduate student instructors.

Creating Inclusive Classrooms – Fostering Classroom Climate

As discussed above, increasing belonging in undergraduate students depends on both instruction methods and classroom culture, both of which are directly affected by an instructor's decisions in the classroom. As teaching assistants, graduate students may have little to no control on the content or activities assigned in a course, but they certainly have control over how the material is presented in their lab section and how classroom climate is established and maintained. Classroom climate is the combined intellectual, emotional, social, and physical environments that students exist and learn in (Ambrose et al., 2010). Classroom climate is not fixed. This means it might be perceived differently based on student background. Classroom climate also might vary throughout a term. It is up to the instructor to maintain a positive, inclusive classroom climate for the duration of a course.

Below, you will find some practices for creating an inclusive classroom climate. Please note that this is by no means a comprehensive list. Additionally, this list should not be viewed as

a “checklist for inclusion” – cultivating inclusive classrooms is a lifelong practice that requires more care, intention, and nuance than checking the boxes on a to-do list!

- **Consider your own social identity.** Social identity is the unique intersection of the many groups that we belong to in society. For example, gender, race, and socioeconomic status are some groups which factor into a social identity. Membership to these groups may be internally identified or externally prescribed by societal perception (Ellemers et al., 2002). Membership of certain groups bestows individuals with power and privilege, while membership of others results in oppression and marginalization. Members of the majority “in groups” may be unaware of the perspective, needs, and oppression of the minority “out groups.” It is important, then, that we understand our own social identities before entering the classroom and how our identities position us in a social structure. Awareness of our own privileges and power, and what it might mean for students who do not share those identities, sets us up to better acknowledge, accommodate, and celebrate the differences amongst the students in a course.
- **Make the most of the first day.** Research has shown that the first day of a course has lasting impacts for the rest of the term (Hermann et al., 2010). The culture, expectations, and attitude you establish during the first session of the term can determine the sense of belonging and student success for the entire course. The first day is the best opportunity to intentionally establish mutual respect and cooperation as the classroom norm, as well as position yourself as an empathetic instructor who values individual identity and collective community. This can be accomplished in a variety of simple ways, some of which will be discussed below.
- **Introduce your complete self.** On the first day, model openness as a classroom norm by sharing some personal aspects of yourself, going beyond simply your name. This might include your professional or academic history, your social identities, or something you enjoy outside of your career. For example, you might share your pronouns, how you came to be a geologist, or a hobby that is important to you. You need not share deeply intimate details, but sharing some of your identities with your students communicates that you believe identity is important in your classroom. Additionally, sharing non-academic information about yourself humanizes the classroom and implicitly acknowledges that your classroom does not exist in a vacuum, which is an important influence on student belonging (Pacansky-Brock et al., 2020). You and your students all have backgrounds that influence how you engage with the course at hand, and initiating conversation about identity reinforces that this is important to you as an instructor.
- **Get to know your complete students,** not only as learners but as whole people. Cohen and Garcia (2008) show that potentially the most important factor in ensuring student salience and retention is the demonstration that the student is part of a collective

positive experience in the classroom. Building community within your classroom requires that you know who you are teaching, what their histories are, and how they are feeling about the course (Dewsbury, 2020). This information can be systematically and respectfully collected using a first-day info sheet (Killpack & Mélon, 2020) or a “Who’s in Class?” form (Addy et al., 2021), as well as spontaneously through casual interactions with your students. You can use this information to purposefully craft how you approach teaching and in-class activities, engage with your students on a personal level, and direct students to relevant on-campus resources, if necessary.

- **Offer an unyielding welcome.** The sense of belonging is greatly influenced by the events of the first day of class, but it is continually reinforced throughout the rest of the term as well. As such, you should prioritize a welcoming environment during every class session, not just the first! This can be fostered by being empathetic to students, approaching classroom policies with kindness, and encouraging interaction outside of the classroom, between you and the students *and* between the students and their fellow classmates.
- **Be transparent.** Transparency in all facets of the classroom encourages student participation and fosters the communal nature of learning (Anderson et al., 2013). This applies to both the practical aspects of classroom operation and the emotional support of your student body. Practically, you should be clear about the expectations you have for your students, such as attendance and attitude. Additionally, you should be explicit about policies as they relate to your students’ work, such as grading and late policies, and you should communicate the expected timetable for them to receive feedback from you on their work. Being transparent about these aspects of the classroom helps mitigate student anxieties and reduces friction throughout the semester (Thompson, 2007). On the personal side, you should be transparent that your role is to help students reach the goals of the course, and that you believe they are capable of doing so. This can also look like acknowledging feelings of imposter syndrome in yourself and in your students, admitting when you don’t know an answer, and recognizing that course content is indeed difficult at times. Reframing struggle as an important component of learning, rather than a personal failing, has been shown to dramatically increase student retention in STEM programs (Walton & Cohen, 2011).
- **Listen to your students, and respond to their feedback.** Communication is crucial for building a welcoming classroom which serves *all* of your students. Additionally, students will have a most vested interest in the class community if they feel they have a true say in how the class is run (Al-Baharani 2022). Additionally, soliciting and, importantly, enacting student suggestions fosters a welcoming environment in which communication and learning go both ways. You can solicit feedback before, during, and after the course to maximize the effectiveness of this technique. With pre-course

feedback, you can gather information about your students as learners, their needs that they are already aware of, and how to best engage the students in the course content. Mid-course feedback allows you to adjust your approach in accordance with new or developing needs the students have as well as to simply hear from the student perspective on what works and what does not in the course. It is important that you not only solicit the feedback, but also acknowledge it. You do not have to employ every single suggestion from every single student, but you should acknowledge what was suggested and why you are choosing not to enact it. Finally, post-course feedback offers you a chance to solicit information about the course in its entirety and adjust as needed for future iterations. Collecting student feedback both engages students in the active building of their education as well as provides you with important contextual information with which you can refine your teaching approach.

- **Be aware of, and prepared to respond to, microaggressions in the classroom.** A microaggression is a subtle form of prejudice directed at members of marginalized groups. Microaggressions are often both unintentional and brief, making them difficult to recognize from the outside. However, microaggressions occur frequently in college classrooms, and they put undue stress on students who hold marginalized identities (Sue et al., 2007; Boysen, 2012). Knowing that microaggressions are prevalent in all classrooms, you will be better equipped to identify them when they do occur. Addressing microaggressions can be intimidating and awkward, in part because it requires conversations about difficult topics, but also because microaggressions are more nebulous than an act of explicit prejudice. Some instructors might be inclined to ignore a microaggression to avoid calling attention to the negative behavior. However, studies have shown that students prefer that an instructor explicitly call out and address microaggressions when they occur (Boysen, 2012 and references therein). Not reacting to an incident is, in itself, a response. Nonengagement implies that you are permissive of the microaggression which occurred in your classroom. It is imperative that you respond when a microaggression has occurred, but research shows that it does not need to be an immediate nor direct confrontation. A class-wide discussion is an equally suitable response because it lessens the intensity of the confrontation and can elucidate the problematic nature of an action or event that some students might otherwise not have noticed (Boysen 2012). Identifying and responding to microaggressions is important for maintaining mutual respect in your classroom community and enhances marginalized students' sense of belonging.

Creating Inclusive Classrooms – Encouraging Learning for All

Just as it is important to foster an inclusive classroom climate, it is important to utilize inclusive pedagogical techniques when teaching. Inclusive pedagogy maximizes student

learning by incorporating an understanding of how new knowledge is acquired while also proactively addressing and accounting for barriers in the classroom.

Active Learning

Traditionally, classrooms are viewed as a one-way conveyance of information from an instructor to their students. However, research has shown that students learn best when they engage personally with course material and construct their own understanding of new information (Bereiter 1994). Importantly, this means that student learning is impacted not only by what instructors do in the classroom, but also by the student's own background, preconceptions, and experiences. This concept is referred to as the constructivist theory of learning, in which student experiences in and out of the classroom are critical for their development of new knowledge.

Constructivism is most typically applied in college classrooms through the employment of active learning techniques. Active learning techniques are broadly defined as activities or methods that require students to be actively engaged with the material and produce higher order thinking about the content (Bonwell and Eison, 1991). Higher order thinking is any thought process which requires the assimilation of old and new information, particularly for application to new situations (Lewis & Smith, 1993). Active learning techniques vary from very simple, such as including intentional pauses in a lecture for students to think, to more involved, such as multi-group collaborative projects. Some active learning techniques are listed below. Note that these are often intended for use during a primary lecture but can be easily modified and applied in lab sections as well!

- **Pause Procedure:** At various points throughout a lecture, pause for two minutes. In an hour-long lecture, you might pause two or three times. During the pause, encourage students to engage in activities like identifying their confusions, comparing notes with other students, or summarizing the chunk of the lecture that preceded the pause. Encourage students to ask questions at this time. This method aids student learning by having them reflect on the content and check their own understanding. Additionally, this method breaks long lectures up into more digestible chunks, which gives structure to the lesson that can aid the emphasis of important themes and concepts.
- **Muddiest Point:** At the end of a class session or course topic, ask students to write down and turn in their muddiest point, or their biggest outstanding question. In the next class session, be sure to address the most common themes reported in the class's muddiest points. This method requires that students identify and articulate their weakest areas in the course material, which engages them in critical thinking and self-reflection.
- **Think-Pair-Share:** Pose a question or prompt to the class for students to consider individually. Then, have students pair up to share and discuss their answers. Finally,

have some or all of the groups report the results of their discussions to the whole class. This method gives students the opportunity to practice articulating newly formed thoughts, as well as gauge their understanding of a topic through collaborative discussion.

- **Classroom Polling:** Periodically throughout a class session, prompt the students with a question and record their answers in a poll. This can be done formally with a paid software, like Top Hat or iClicker, or more informally by having students raise their hands or hand in slips of paper. This can be done in pairs or individually. This method provides students the opportunity to self-assess their understanding, identify weak areas, and requires they engage directly with the material.
- **Jigsaw Method:** Divide students into Expert Groups where each group is responsible for understanding, assessing, and/or analyzing a different component of a course topic. When the Expert Groups are finished with their portion of the activity, reassign groups so that each group has one expert from each Expert Group. Each expert then teaches the mixed group about their expertise, and all experts must work together to address large-scale prompts or questions that rely on the knowledge of all the experts. This method requires both self- and peer-teaching, which yields a deeper understanding of material than traditional assessment alone, and promotes development of a science identity because students are personally responsible for contributing knowledge to the group.
- **Minute Paper:** At some point in a class session, give students one to three minutes to write down everything they know about a topic previously covered in class. Have students share their thoughts with a partner and/or the class as a whole. This method encourages student reflection and collaboration.
- **Student-Generated Test Questions:** Have students work together or individually to write a test question at the end of a unit or topic. If the questions are written individually, have the students discuss the questions they wrote in small groups after and pick a group favorite. Share the groups' favorite questions as a class. It may also be helpful to distribute all the test questions to the class as a study guide. This method encourages students to synthesize course material, identify important concepts, and collaborate with others to compare priorities in the material.
- **Word Journal:** Have students describe a topic or unit with a single word. Then, have them explain their word choice with a short paragraph. This method encourages metacognition by making students reflect on how they know what they know, as well as providing an assessment of class understanding on a topic.

While active learning is shown to improve student learning, reduce the achievement gap in diverse student bodies (Handelsman et al., 2007), and increase student retention in STEM programs (Prince & Felder, 2007), it may not be received well by the students due to the

increased perception of struggle (DesLauriers et al., 2011). Additionally, active learning strategies are not innately inclusive to all students. Therefore, it is important that instructors intentionally make their active learning techniques an inclusive and equitable practice for all students. Consider the following techniques to achieve inclusivity with active learning:

- **Set expectations clearly.** Communicating your expectations with your students sets them up to succeed. Additionally, students may respond better to active learning approaches if the evidence and reasoning behind them is explained up front. When discussing your use of active learning, you can key your students in on the kinds of activities you plan to use, why they are beneficial, and what the students can expect from the experience. It's a good idea to communicate that active learning can feel more difficult than more traditional techniques or activities, but that the struggle is part of the benefit. This way, you students are primed to trust the process rather than blame their own perceived deficiencies for their struggles in class.
- **Adopt an asset-based approach.** An asset-based approach in the classroom is one which emphasizes the skills and abilities that every student brings to the classroom, rather than deficits (Johnson, 2019). You can conduct an asset activity with the students in your course. To do this, have the students make a collaborative list of skills a successful scientist should have. Invariably, most of the list will be things scientists *do* rather than *know*, such as being perseverant, accepting constructive criticism, and being creative in the face of challenge. Have students identify skills from the list that they see in themselves and encourage a discussion on the unique combinations of skills each person brings to the classroom. However, if conducting such an activity isn't possible, you can foster an asset-based classroom by the way you discuss group work or learning achievements. Emphasize throughout the term that all students bring something to the table that is useful for achieving the goals of the course and completing the active learning activities.
- **Encourage a growth mindset.** Active learning can be a difficult experience for some students because it inherently requires students to grapple directly with difficult concepts. Even though struggle in classroom settings leads to higher cognitive processing (Lepper & Woolverton, 2002), your students may be unfamiliar and uncomfortable with the experience. In turn, this struggle may make your students feel poorly about their own abilities and make them question their role in the course or program (DesLauriers et al., 2011). One way to mitigate these imposter feelings in your students is to encourage a growth mindset. The growth mindset states that intelligence and learning are not fixed features. Rather, they can be developed and fostered with work and effort, which might feel like struggle at times. Remind your students that learning is

difficult, especially as course material gets more complex, and regularly emphasize that you believe they can all achieve what you've asked of them.

- **Be flexible in your application.** Active learning requires that students engage personally with the course content, but different students will be more or less engaged depending on the technique used. To combat this, you should offer several ways to complete an active learning task, whenever possible. For example, you might allow students to complete a Minute Paper activity in text, audio, or video format. Allowing students to choose the mode of application means the students can use the methods that they know work best for them in their learning.
- **Check in frequently.** Your students' needs may change over the course of a semester, so it is important to solicit feedback from them frequently. This way, you can ensure you are optimizing the learning opportunities for all your students. Additionally, it is important to check in frequently when students work together in groups. Whether the group work is limited to one class session or spans an entire term, checking in and redirecting where necessary will improve the experience for all students and ensure that all members feel valued.

Universal Design for Learning

The Center for Applied Special Technology (CAST) has developed guiding principles which collectively are known as the Universal Design for Learning (UDL). UDL is a proactive approach to course design that is underpinned by the idea that students learn best when they are given many different opportunities to learn, apply, and assess information. Importantly, UDL emphasizes including a myriad of learning experiences in order to accommodate the diverse body of learners in the classroom. There are three guidelines for UDL:

- **Provide multiple means of representation.** This guideline encourages instructors to use a variety of methods to convey new information or concepts to students (Izzo et al., 2008). For instance, using lectures, videos, and group discussions at different points during a course. This additionally refers to being flexible and clear with language in the classroom, such as displaying a mathematical equation in symbols as well as in plain language words.
- **Provide multiple means of engagement.** Student learning hinges on student engagement, and it is the instructor's responsibility to provide all students with modes of engagement that get them excited about learning. This can be accomplished by using real-world examples that reflect your student community and demonstrate the applicability of the information to real problems. Additionally, offering variable methods

for completing assignments will ensure every student is given the opportunity to work in a fashion that works best for them.

- **Provide multiple means of action and expression.** Students demonstrate their learning through assessments, traditionally in the form of midterms and finals. However, for a multitude of reasons, not all students may be able to demonstrate their learning with this kind of assessment, even if they have successfully learned the content. For this reason, it is preferable that an instructor offers multiple kinds of assessments throughout a course. For example, written reports, presentations, and multimedia projects require that students use different skills to communicate their learning. This might also take the form of accepting multiple forms of response on a traditional exam, such as bullet points, pictures, or written paragraphs.

Taken together, these guidelines aim to produce students who are resourceful and knowledgeable, purposeful and motivated, and strategic and goal oriented (CAST, 2018).

As a graduate student, you likely will not have control over the design of a course or lab section that you are asked to teach, but it is still useful context to keep these principles of UDL in mind. While you may not be in a position to change course structure, assignments, or content, you can motivate your approach to the given materials with UDL. For example, you can give a pre-lab lecture that uses variable representations and engages students in a different way than the lab assignment itself.

Other Resources

For the sake of accessibility, this document has only briefly summarized the broad strokes of inclusive and effective teaching. As a result, the full complexity and nuance of these topics could not be fully explored. To supplement this summary document, please consult the resources listed below, as well as the references cited throughout this document.

Inclusive Teaching & DEI

- [Inclusive STEM Teaching Project](#)
- [Center for the Integration of Research, Teaching, and Learning](#)
- [Evidence Based Teaching Guide: Inclusive Teaching, The American Society for Cell Biology – Life Sciences Education](#)
- [Inclusive Teaching Toolkit, Center for the Advancement of Teaching Excellence, University of Illinois Chicago](#)
- [Inclusion in practice: a systematic review of diversity-focused STEM programming in the United States, Palid et al. \(2023\)](#)
- [How to Center DEI in Teaching, Eberly Center, Carnegie Mellon University](#)

Active Learning

- [Active Learning Techniques, University of Michigan](#)
- [226 Active Learning Techniques, Center for Excellence in Teaching and Learning, Iowa State University](#)
- [ABLConnect, The Derek Bok Center for Teaching and Learning, Harvard University](#)
- [Active Learning Resources, Teaching in Higher Ed](#)
- [Inquiry-Based Learning, The Schreyer Institute for Teaching Excellence, Penn State](#)

Course Design

- [Universal Design for Learning, Center for Applied Special Technologies \(CAST\)](#)
- [Course Design Resources, Digital Learning, UC San Diego](#)
- [Inclusive Course Design, Center for Teaching Innovation, Cornell University](#)
- [Backward Design Basics, Cult of Pedagogy](#)
- [5 Research-Based Tips for Providing Students with Meaningful Feedback, edutopia](#)
- [Classroom Assessment Techniques \(CATs\), Center for Teaching, Vanderbilt University](#)

Penn State Resources

- [The John A. Dutton Institute for Teaching and Learning Excellence](#)
 - Director of Learning Design: Stevie Rocco, sxr133@psu.edu
 - [Flexible Instruction Teaching Guide](#)
 - [15 Ways to Get Started with Diversity, Equity, Inclusion, and Belonging](#)
 - Access to learning designers, teaching consultations, course content development assistance, and more!
- [Schreyer Institute for Teaching Excellence](#)
 - [Course in College Teaching](#)
 - [Universal Design for Learning](#)
 - [Events and Workshops](#)
- [Graduate School Teaching Certificate](#)
- [Graduate Student Online Teaching Certificate](#)
- [Teaching and Learning with Technology](#)
- [LinkedIn Learning](#)
- [Accessibility and Usability at Penn State](#)
- GEOSC 597 - Teaching Seminar
 - Instructor: Tanya Furman (tfl3@psu.edu)
 - Typically offered in Spring
- Peer Teaching Assessment Committee
 - Current members: Leah Youngquist (2023-2024)

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